

A Study on Group B Streptococcal Colonization in Pregnant Women- A Prospective Observational Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Group B Streptococcus (GBS), a leading cause of neonatal and maternal morbidity, is responsible for early-onset disease (EOD) in neonates and conditions like chorioamnionitis in mothers. GBS colonisation in pregnant women can lead to vertical transmission during labour. Although universal screening has significantly reduced neonatal GBS disease in developed nations, its implementation in developing countries, including India, remains limited. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of GBS colonisation among pregnant women, assess associated maternal and neonatal outcomes, and propose an optimal screening strategy.

Materials and Methods: This prospective observational study included 125 pregnant women between 35–37 weeks gestation at Shridevi Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Hospital, Tumkur, Karnataka, over 12 months. Vaginal and rectal swabs were collected, cultured using enrichment broth and sheep blood agar, and analysed using standard microbiological methods. Maternal demographic details, obstetric history, and neonatal outcomes were recorded.

Results: GBS colonisation prevalence was 4% (5/125). Colonisation was identified in 40% of vaginal swabs, 40% of anal swabs, and 20% of both. GBS positivity was significantly associated with premature rupture of membranes ($p = 0.0017$) but not with age, gravidity, or socioeconomic status. No maternal or neonatal morbidity was observed in GBS-positive cases. Neonates of colonised mothers showed no NICU admissions or clinical signs of sepsis.

Conclusion: GBS colonisation among pregnant women was low (4%) and significantly associated with PROM. Enhanced detection using dual-site sampling and targeted prophylaxis may mitigate adverse outcomes. More extensive studies are required to inform GBS prevention strategies in India.

Keywords: Group B Streptococcus, Prevalence, Neonatal Outcomes.

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Introduction

Group B Streptococcus (GBS), also known as Streptococcus agalactiae, is a significant pathogen contributing to maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality worldwide. [1] Approximately 15–40% of healthy individuals harbour GBS in their gastrointestinal or lower genital tract; asymptomatic colonisation in the vaginal and rectal areas is common, serving as a critical source for vertical transmission to neonates during labour. [2]

This transmission is the most frequent cause of neonatal infections within the first seven days of life (early-onset disease, EOD), with an estimated incidence ranging from 0.17 to 3.06 per 1,000 live births in developing countries. [3] EOD is primarily respiratory distress, sepsis, and pneumonia, often leading to high neonatal morbidity and mortality

rates of 10–20%. Late-onset disease (LOD), occurring between seven days and three months of age, manifests mainly as meningitis. [4] GBS-related neonatal morbidity is a healthcare challenge, with preterm deliveries, premature or prolonged rupture of membranes, and intrapartum fever among its notable risk factors. For mothers, GBS can cause chorioamnionitis tract infections and postpartum endometritis, contributing to significant maternal morbidity. [5]

Preventive strategies for neonatal GBS infection risk-based and culture-based approaches. The risk-based method administers intrapartum antibiotic prophylaxis (IAP) when risk factors are identified, while the culture-based strategy screens all pregnant women for GBS colonisation between 35–

37 weeks of gestation. In the United States, universal screening combined with IAP recently reduced neonatal GBS disease incidence from 2–3 cases per 1,000 live births to 0.34–0.37 cases. [6] However, the GBS screening and prevention strategy is widely implemented in countries like India. While Indian studies report GBS colonisation rates between 1.76% and 16%, neonatal transmission rates of 53–56% are comparable to those in developed nations. [7]

The limited recognition of GBS as a clinical problem in India is compounding the bacterium, likely due to competition with other bacteria or suboptimal culture techniques. In our hospital, frequent pathogens in neonatal sepsis include *Klebsiella*, *E. coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, with no reported cases of GBS isolation. This suggests a need for improved culture methods and screening protocols.

This prospective observational study aims to determine the prevalence of GBS colonisation in the pre-use of appropriate sample collection and culture media. It also seeks to assess maternal and neonatal outcomes among colonised women, ultimately proposing an optimal screening strategy to reduce neonatal EOD in our population.

Materials and Methods

This prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Shridevi Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Hospital, Tumkur, Karnataka, over 12 months from June 2020 to 2021. Pregnant women at 35 to 37 weeks of gestation attending the antenatal outpatient department (OPD) were recruited based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Women willing to provide informed consent were included. At the same time, those who had undergone pelvic examinations within two weeks, received antibiotics in the preceding two weeks, experienced antepartum haemorrhage, or were unwilling to follow up for delivery and NICU care were excluded. The sample size was determined using the formula for prevalence studies, assuming a Group B Streptococcus (GBS) colonisation prevalence of 13%, with 95% confidence and 6% precision. A

sample size of 121 was calculated, and four additional cases were included to account for potential loss to follow-up, resulting in a final sample size of 125. Participants were recruited after obtaining ethical clearance from the institutional review board, and informed consent was secured before data collection.

Vaginal and rectal swabs were collected from participants using aseptic techniques and inoculated into an enrichment broth containing gentamycin and nalidixic acid. The broth was incubated overnight at 37°C, and subcultures were made on 5% sheep blood agar, followed by incubation for 18–24 hours. Colonies suggestive of GBS were identified through standard microbiological methods, including smear microscopy, catalase tests, and bacitracin susceptibility, with confirmation using the VITEK automated system. Data on maternal demographic details, obstetric history, and risk factors, including preterm labour, rupture of membranes, and intrapartum fever, were recorded.

GBS-positive women received intrapartum antibiotic prophylaxis with cefazolin, following hospital antibiotic policy. Newborns of colonised mothers were swabbed from the umbilical region, external ear, and nose within one hour of delivery and before their first bath. Neonatal outcomes, including GBS colonisation, birth weight, NICU admissions, and clinical signs of sepsis, were recorded. Maternal outcomes such as febrile morbidity, wound infections, and urinary tract infections were also monitored. Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 22, with significance at $p < 0.05$.

Results

125 pregnant women were included in the study, with a prevalence of Group B Streptococcus (GBS) colonisation observed in 4% (5/125) of the participants. Among the GBS-positive women, 40% had vaginal swab positivity, 40% had anal swab positivity, and 20% were positive in both samples (Table 1). The remaining 96% of participants were GBS-negative, highlighting this population's low prevalence of colonization.

Table 1: Prevalence and Sample Distribution of Group B Streptococcus (N=125)

Parameter		Frequency	Percentage
GBS Status	Positive	5	4.0%
	Negative	120	96.0%
Sample Type (GBS Positive)	Vaginal Swab	2	1.6%
	Anal Swab	2	1.6%
	Both Vaginal & Anal	1	0.8%

The analysis of age distribution indicated that GBS positivity was highest in the 31–35 age group, accounting for 60% of cases, while 40% were in the

20–25 years group. No positive cases were found in the 26–30 or 36–40 age groups. Among GBS-negative participants, 51.66% were in the 26–30

years group, followed by 31.66% in the 20–25 years group and 15.83% in the 31–35 years group,

with one participant in the 36–40 years group (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Age Distribution

Risk factor analysis demonstrated a significant association between GBS colonisation and premature rupture of membranes (PROM).

The odds of PROM were substantially higher in GBS-positive women compared to their GBS-negative counterparts ($p = 0.0017$). No significant

associations were identified between GBS colonisation and gravidity ($p = 0.2538$) or socioeconomic status ($p = 0.4201$) (Table 2).

Among the GBS-positive women, 80% belonged to the middle socioeconomic class, while 20% were in the lower class.

Table 2: Association of GBS Colonization with Risk Factors (N=125)

Risk Factor		GBS Positive (%)	GBS Negative (%)	p-value
Gravidity	Primigravida	2 (40%)	78 (65%)	0.2538
	Multigravida	3 (60%)	42 (35%)	
PROM	Yes	2 (40%)	6 (5%)	0.0017
	No	3 (60%)	114 (95%)	
Socioeconomic Status	Lower Class	1 (20%)	7 (5.83%)	0.4201
	Middle Class	4 (80%)	109 (90.83%)	
	Upper Class	0 (0%)	4 (3.3%)	

Regarding maternal and neonatal outcomes, the majority of GBS-positive women (60%) delivered vaginally, while 40% underwent cesarean section (primarily for obstetric indications). Among neonates born to GBS-positive mothers, none required NICU admission, and their birth weights ranged between 2.5 kg and >3 kg. Comparatively, 2.5% of

neonates born to GBS-negative mothers required NICU admission. No maternal morbidity, such as puerperal sepsis or wound infections, was observed in GBS-positive women (Table 3). These findings suggest that while GBS colonisation is associated with PROM, its impact on maternal and neonatal outcomes in this population was minimal.

Table 3: Maternal and Neonatal Outcomes by GBS Status (N=125)

Outcome		GBS Positive (%)	GBS Negative (%)	p-value
Mode of Delivery	Normal Vaginal Delivery	3 (60%)	101 (84.17%)	0.1690
	LSCS	2 (40%)	14 (11.67%)	
	Forceps/Vacuum	0 (0%)	5 (4.17%)	
Birth Weight	2-2.49 kg	0 (0%)	7 (5.83%)	0.8163
	2.5–3 kg	2 (40%)	53 (44.17%)	
	>3 kg	3 (60%)	60 (50%)	
NICU Admission	Yes	0 (0%)	3 (2.5%)	0.7204
	No	5 (100%)	117 (97.5%)	

Discussion

Group B Streptococcus (GBS) has been recognized as a significant contributor to perinatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in developed nations where it is a leading cause of neonatal sepsis and meningitis. Despite its importance, limited data exist regarding GBS prevalence and associated maternal and neonatal outcomes in developing countries. The current study, conducted on a cohort of 125 pregnant women, observed a GBS colonisation prevalence of 4%, aligning with previous Indian studies by Dilshad Arif et al. [8] and Selvarani et al. [9], which also reported rates of 4%. These figures are notably lower than those reported in studies from other regions, such as Agricola Joachim et al. [10] (23%) and J. Motlova et al. [11] (29.3%), emphasising the geographical and demographic variability in GBS colonisation rates.

Detection rates were enhanced by simultaneous rectovaginal sampling, with 40% of GBS-positive cases identified in vaginal swabs, 40% in anal swabs, and 20% in both. This corroborates findings from studies like those by KP Patil et al. [12] and Vijayan Sharmila et al. [13], highlighting the importance of dual-site sampling for accurate detection. In our study, GBS colonisation was not significantly associated with age, gravidity, or socioeconomic status. However, there was a notable trend of higher colonisation among multigravida women (60%) and those aged 31–35 (60%).

A significant association was observed between GBS colonisation and premature rupture of membranes (PROM), with 40% of GBS-positive women experiencing PROM. This finding is consistent with studies like Vijayan Sharmila et al. [13] and Kavitha P. Konikkara et al. [14], which also reported a significant relationship between GBS colonisation and PROM.

However, no association was found between GBS colonisation and adverse neonatal outcomes, such as low birth weight, NICU admission, or neonatal sepsis. This contrasts with some studies showing neonatal GBS colonisation or morbidity, potentially due to differences in sample size, study design, or intrapartum antibiotic prophylaxis (IAP) implementation.

Conclusion

The study highlights a GBS colonization prevalence of 4% among pregnant women, with enhanced detection achieved through rectovaginal sampling. GBS colonization was significantly associated with PROM but showed no significant relationship with gravidity, age, socioeconomic status, or adverse neonatal outcomes.

The absence of neonatal morbidity or maternal morbidity underscores the potential benefits of early detection and targeted interventions. Further research with larger cohorts and longer durations is warranted to establish robust associations and inform preventive strategies in the Indian context.

References

1. Dechen TC, Sumit K, Ranabir P. Correlates of vaginal colonization with group B streptococci among pregnant women. *Journal of global infectious diseases*. 2010; 2(3):236.
2. Onipede A, Adefusi O, Adeyemi A, Adejuyigbe E, Oyelese A, Ogunniyi T. Group B Streptococcus carriage during late pregnancy in Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *African Journal of Clinical and Experimental Microbiology*. 2012; 13(3): 135-43.
3. Xie Y, Yang J, Zhao P, Jia H, Wang Q. Occurrence and detection method evaluation of group B streptococcus from prenatal vaginal specimen in Northwest China. *Diagnostic pathology*. 2016; 11(1):8.
4. Onwuezobe IA, Effiom RA. Prevalence and associated risk factors of group B streptococcus in pregnant women attending antenatal care in a Nigerian urban hospital. *Ibom Medical Journal*. 2016;9(1):1-7
5. Mahtab S, Madewell ZJ, Madhi SA, et al. Stillbirths and Neonatal Deaths Caused by Group B Streptococcus in Africa and South Asia Identified Through Child Health and Mortality Prevention Surveillance (CHAMPS). *Open Forum Infectious Diseases*. 2023; 10(9):1-12.
6. Van Dyke MK, Phares CR, Lynfield R, Thomas AR, Arnold KE, Craig AS, Mohle-Boetani J, Gershman K, Schaffner W, Petit S, Zansky SM. Evaluation of universal antenatal screening for group B streptococcus. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2009; 360(25):2626-36.
7. Shet A, Ferrieri P. Neonatal & maternal group B streptococcal infections: a comprehensive review. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*. 2004; 120(3):141-150.
8. Arif D, Urehkar AD, Kore A, Chaudhary BL, Nissar J, Singh S. Prevalence of Streptococcus agalactiae in Pregnant Women and its Antibiotic Sensitivity Pattern. *Int J Curr Microbiol App Sci*. 2015; 4(7):315-20.
9. Selvarani, Mallika, Abi. The association of Maternal Vaginal Colonization of Group B Streptococci (GBS) and Preterm labour. *Int. J. Modn. Res. Revs*. 2015; 3(10):896-898.
10. Joachim A, Matee MI, Massawe FA, Lyamuya EF. Maternal and neonatal colonisation of group B streptococcus at Muhimbili National Hospital in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania: prevalence, risk factors and antimicrobial resistance. *BMC Public Health*. 2009; 9:437.

11. Motlova J, Strakova L, Urbaskova P, Sak P, Sever T. Vaginal & rectal carriage of *Streptococcus agalactiae* in the Czech Republic: incidence, serotypes distribution & susceptibility to antibiotics. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*. 2004 May 2; 119:84.
12. Patil KP, Singla SS, Nagmoti MB, Swamy MK. Group B streptococci colonization in pregnant women: is screening necessary? *J South Asian Fed Obstet Gynaecol*. 2013; 5:64-7.
13. Sharmila V, Babu TA, Chaturvedula L. Neonatal outcome in maternal genital tract group B streptococcal colonization. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2016; 5(10):3444-7.
14. Konikkara KP, Baliga S, Shenoy SM, Bharati B. Comparison of various culture methods for isolation of Group B *Streptococcus* from intrapartum vaginal colonization. *Journal of laboratory physicians*. 2013; 5(1):42.